

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT
GPR	2010	B		Min: 63.1767 Max: 63.2888	1215 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropogenic

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 1142-1145 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: *Crushed tufo floor in corridoio I*

Covered by: SU: 1182 Fills: SU: Filled by: SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX				
☐ Pottery ☐ Nails ☐ Tiles ☐ Marble ☐ Amphorae ☐ Quarried debris ☐ Dolia ☐ Slag ☐ Brick ☐ Mosaic tile(s) ☐ Basalt slabs ☐ Mortar ☐ Opus signinum ☐ Coins ☐ Painted plaster ☐ Metal (specify) ☐ Burnt Adobe ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Other (specify) ☐ Glass	☐ Tufo (specify) ☐ Travertine ☐ Other Limestone ☐ Basalt ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☐ Pebbles (range) ☐ Gravel (range)	☐ Charcoal ☐ Ash ☐ Animal bones ☐ Human bones ☐ Animal teeth ☐ Human teeth ☐ Shells ☐ Other (specify)	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% ☐ Granular ☐ Layered ☐ Cohesive <table border="1"> <tr> <th>Compaction</th> <th>Color</th> </tr> <tr> <td> ☒ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft </td> <td> ☐ Black ☐ Brown ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☒ Other (specify) <i>orange</i> </td> </tr> </table>	Compaction	Color	☒ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft	☐ Black ☐ Brown ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☒ Other (specify) <i>orange</i>
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to: *1216, 1255* Is bound to (only for masonry):

Is abutted by: Abuts: *1183, 1188*

Is covered by: Covers:

Is cut by: *1191, 1186, 1182* Cuts:

Is filled by: Fills:

OBSERVATIONS: *dry, hot conditions, excavated with pickaxe & trowel*

DESCRIPTION

Position within sector: *central part of trench B 2010*

Shape: *long rectangular*

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): *very gentle slope to the south*

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): *thickness is constant ca. 0,05m*

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

1276 1255

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify) *crushed tufo*

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

*Very orange red (heated?)
 tufo fragments of a size
 up to 5cm Ø, which
 have been compacted to
 a very solid floor surface.
 In some parts there is
 an even layer of white-
 wash! on top of it.*

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

See front

INTERPRETATION

*tufo floor within corridor? , the corridor evolved
 or was built later into this already existing floor*

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

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